

EDUCATIONAL IDEOLOGY, THE STATE'S DIRECTION OF SOCIAL DEVELOPMENT AND COMPLIANCE WITH NATIONAL VALUES

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***Abstract.** The article describes the importance of educational ideology, the state's direction of social development and compliance with national values. In the paper, ideological worldview is considered as a whole of students' ideas and concepts. The paper discusses that students' ideological outlook should be formed under proper pedagogical control. The author notes that the skills that are significant to fulfill the rules of conduct in the content of citizenship that we have distinguished are not considered contrary to the ideas of scholars who focus on the fact that literacy is a skill when describing different types of literacy.*

***Keywords:** educational ideology, ideological immunity, students, personality qualities, ideological outlook.*

In Uzbekistan, which is being updated in scientific research sources, official documents as well as literature, textbooks and instructional manuals, it is mainly considered as an object for educational influence and formation in the development of students' ideological immunity. In our opinion, the pedagogical conditions for the development of students' ideological immunity in Uzbekistan, which is being renewed under the conditions of Uzbekistan, are much broader and include them than social activity, political and legal personality qualities. Secondly, it is not for nothing that civic literacy is measured by the level of consciousness of students and young people. After all, civic activity is determined by the social consciousness of individuals and motivates them towards active action. And they appear as active subjects who realize their goals and interests.

Ideological worldview is a whole of students' ideas and concepts. In this sense, students' ideological outlook should be formed under proper pedagogical control [1]. As a result of these ideological, pedagogical and preventive factors, the student, that is, a future teacher sets long, medium and short goals and strives to achieve them. He creates his own ideas based on the combination of personal and community interests. According to the research results of sociologist S.S.Otamurodov in the national consciousness stereotypes of Uzbek youth, "Nationality is often identified with religious belief. As a result, national interests are understood in a narrow, religious sense and are not understood at the level of social, national interest. Therefore, moral standards and interests are often separated from social activities, accepted in the form of "fashion and cannot penetrate into the system of self-awareness, so it does not affect the determination of attitude to work" [2].

Ideological-prophylactic knowledge is the protective core of every idea. It is considered as the starting point for independent intellectual activity of the students, and it provides the basis and protects the forces. For this reason, it is an important task of ideological prevention to create real conditions for students to learn. Ideological skill – is formed in the process of students' application

of their knowledge and ideological views. Therefore, learners should be taught to use his ideas and knowledge in the process of education.

The qualification is the ability of students to fully express their ideology and independent thoughts. Systematically establishing the activities of student self-management bodies in higher education and encouraging them morally will have good results. Based on this system, pedagogical conditions are created for students to understand, analyze, plan and implement their ideas. It is also necessary for future teachers to acquire the following special knowledge, skills and qualifications related to ideological prevention:

- 1) Deep understanding of the issue of ideological prevention among adolescents;
- 2) To know the methods of ideological prevention;
- 3) Being able to use ideological prevention tools;
- 4) To know and apply the forms of ideological prevention;
- 5) Good differentiation of the stages of ideological prevention;
- 6) Thorough knowledge of ways to study and improve the effectiveness of ideological prevention.

Ideological pedagogy – as a practical field of pedagogy, studies the principles, forms, methods and tools of ideological-ideological education. The ideology of education is a system of ideas that at the same time responds to the main, very urgent interests of society and the individual. The interaction between the society and the individual takes place in the following form: the society proposes a paradigm for educating new generation and creates the conditions for its implementation, and the young generation, in accordance with the proposed conditions, manifests itself, determines its place and role in the society, and develops itself. Educational ideology, in accordance with the direction of social development of the state and national values, affects the mind of the individual and makes certain changes to his behavior and outlook [3].

The purpose of education is ideology, the main issue of the holistic education system. The goal expresses philosophical, spiritual, moral, economic, political, legal and aesthetic ideas about the “ideal” image of man and society. Currently, an “ideal” young citizen is required to have the following qualities:

- a) Pursuit of happiness and success;
- b) Initiative and innovative thinking;
- c) Assuming responsibility and liability;
- g) Loyalty to the national idea.

Thus, the goal of ideological and ideological education is to form a socially stable person who contributes to raising society to a new level in new socio-economic and political conditions and is capable of self-improvement. The goal of ideological education is achieved by solving specific tasks. Among them, the followings are of particular significance:

- 1) In the conditions of the new socio-political and economic development of the society, orientation of the person to humane and vitally important values, determination of his place in society and determination of life goals, self-awareness and formation of humane orientation to the most important needs;
- 2) Formation of national self-awareness, citizenship, patriotism, respect for law and legal procedures, inner peace and self-respect;

3) Education of the need to master universal human values and national culture in students, to strive to create and increase aesthetic values and taste, spiritual and cultural wealth, to form an active participation in the spiritual life of society;

4) Accustom students to observe universal moral norms, national traditions, professional duty, teach them to rationally evaluate the results of their activities;

5) Identification and development of abilities, general and special abilities based on them, formation of individuality of a person, his creative potential, increasing the potential of self-development;

6) The need for work as a primary life necessity, high life values, achieving success, striving for a goal, initiative, nurturing competitiveness in all areas;

7) The need for physical culture and a healthy lifestyle, family care, raising children in a humanitarian and democratic spirit.

Among the main principles of ideological education, the followings can be distinguished:

1) A humanistic approach to the object of education, which requires treatment of a student's personality as a personal value;

2) Spirituality, which shows students' understanding of the spiritual aspect of the meaning of life, the need to master spiritual culture, to observe the universal norms of humanitarian ethics, to form a sense of intelligence and citizenship;

3) Not only the effective implementation of life activities in the conditions of democratic reforms, but also the free education system, democracy, that represents the organization of mutual activities of students and professors based on cooperative pedagogy;

4) Patriotism, which ensures formation of national consciousness, state integrity, mastering and enrichment of national culture in students;

5) Ability to horizontal and vertical mobility in the conditions of democratization of society, competitiveness manifested as the uniqueness of the labor market requiring mastering of new professions;

6) Diversity of thoughts, approaches, ideas in finding solutions to problems; tolerance, reflecting tolerance for other people's opinion, culture, lifestyle, and behavior in accordance with established standards and requirements;

7) Individualization, that is reflected in the direction of personal interests and needs due to the formation of the ability to freely express one's individual characteristics, to show creative activity;

8) Diversity, that includes different options of educational content and technologies.

If certain pedagogical conditions are created for students to acquire social and cultural experience, not only the level of ideological and ideological education will increase, but also the qualities of citizenship and patriotism will be developed. Such prerequisites may include:

1) The existence of opportunities to develop knowledge about the scientific landscape of the world in the educational institution and, relying on this knowledge, to educate students in citizenship and patriotism, to form a system of scientific views and beliefs about the grounds and ways of further development of society;

2) In the course of educational and non-auditory activities, students' mastery of important values and ideas reflecting the essence of concepts such as statehood, as well as "citizenship" and "patriotism", to expand the scope of these concepts, to develop the skills of independent work on information sources related to historical and biographical information;

3) Raising the level of citizenship and patriotism, national self-awareness based on the active involvement of students in the educational work of the higher educational institution in the course of classroom and classroom training;

4) Improvement of the professional training of future teachers on the organization of ideological and ideological education;

5) Creating an educational system based on mutual respect, mutual understanding, and responsible relations in all subjects of the educational process;

6) Employing new approaches, methods and tools to organize the educational process and use of modern technologies in the process of ideological and ideological education.

Pedagogy of cooperation. Collaborative pedagogy is the joint activity of not only teachers with students and colleagues, but also with parents and neighborhood activists in teaching and upbringing that is considered an important step towards the comprehensive development of a person. Joint action with parents, neighborhood activists, non-governmental and non-profit organizations requires their participation in classroom and non-auditory activities, assistance in improving the quality and efficiency of the educational process, joint resolution of existing problems, and creation of an environment of mutual agreement. We determined the content of the motivational-value component based on the rules of M.S.Kagan that value, importance, attitude and B.S.Bratus that value is the meaning of life [4].

It is known that values become a motive if understood and accepted by a person. Based on the research on the problems of citizenship, citizenship, and civic literacy, we distinguished the values that form the content of the motivational-value component of the development of civic literacy. These are: humanitarianism, loyalty, duty, kindness, dignity, independence, patriotism, and diversity of viewpoints, equality before the law, freedom, conscience, tolerance, justice, respect, and respect for the youth.

We support the ideas of I.I.Kravchenko in determining the values that form the content of the motivational-valuable component of the development of civil immunity. He distinguished a set of basic social values: civic values (freedom, equality, etc.), moral values (conscience, honor, etc.), political values (management, decision-making skills, etc.), knowledge-related values (intellectuality, intuition and others. Understanding the ideas of I.I. Kravchenko about the set of social values that was proposed shows that political values are not considered political, because management, decision-making, and other abilities are not values.

In our assumption, not everything that is important for a person should be included in values. Civic and moral values are real values expressed in categories and concepts corresponding to them. These values “arise in object-subject relations, without the quality of the object, other object – human experiences”. Capability does not occur in any other relationship, that is, subject-subject or subject-object. (Here we do not mean the relationships in which this or that ability of a person is expressed, or rather formed).

We regard the moral component as necessary in terms of the implementation of cognitive and motivational-value components through it. Verbs are used to refer to or addressing someone. As it was stated by V.A. Vasilenko, it can be considered to be realized when there is a certain subjective impact on the recipient of the information directed to him within the framework of the implemented behavior. As V.A.Vasilenko pointed out, behavior does not necessarily end with a subjective impact on the mind of the addressee.

Therefore, if any action is considered without analyzing the expressed relations, regardless of its moral, i.e., civic significance, then any of these actions is an operation. If the action is considered not according to the way of its implementation, but from the point of view of its moral significance, then this is the behavior of the student. In the development of civic literacy the followings are considered: the ability to put other people in their place through understanding (expressing empathy); and the ability to follow the laws and rules of common living in society. As we can see, that the skills necessary to fulfill the rules of conduct in the content of citizenship, that we have distinguished, are not considered contrary to the ideas of scholars who focus on the fact that literacy is a skill when describing different types of literacy.

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